

Cultural Interactions through the Lens of Pottery: Analysis of the Late La Tène Assemblage from Northwestern Bohemia

Jan Volf, Karel Slavíček, Kristýna Trnová

Corresponding author

JAN VOLF, Institute of Archaeology of the CAS, Prague, Letenská 4, CZ-118 01, Praha, Czechia, volf@arup.cas.cz, ORCID 0000-0003-0126-5767

KAREL SLAVÍČEK, Department of Geological Sciences, Faculty of Science, Masaryk University, Kotlářská 2, CZ-611 37, Brno, Czechia; slav.karel@sci.muni.cz, ORCID 0000-0002-6662-927X

KRISTÝNA TRNOVÁ, Department of Geological Sciences, Faculty of Science, Masaryk University, Kotlářská 2, CZ-611 37, Brno, Czechia, 393742@mail.muni.cz

Abstract

During the first century BC, significant social, economic, and cultural changes took place in Bohemia and other parts of Central Europe, culminating in the second half of the century. This transformation is traditionally interpreted as the result of population movements. Assemblages dated to the first half of the first century BC from Northwestern Bohemia, including Lužice, occupy a specific position in this interpretation, as they contain pottery attributable to both the local La Tène and the Przeworsk cultures. Previous studies linked these assemblages with the first wave of incoming communities preceding later, larger-scale migrations.

However, these assemblages have so far been studied primarily through stylistic analysis. To better understand the relationships between pottery attributable to distinct archaeological cultures, we analysed pottery from Lužice using macroscopic observation, X-ray fluorescence (XRF), and thin-section analysis.

Results showed that pottery of both cultures was made from similar materials, with no material group being exclusive to Przeworsk pottery. Greater differences were observed in manufacturing techniques and visual attributes. The use of comparable ceramic materials does not contradict the possibility of contemporaneous production. However, producers of La Tène and Przeworsk pottery preserved their respective pottery styles, which may have served as markers of social identity.

Keywords

La Tène Period - pottery production - socio-economic network - chemical composition analysis - thin-section analysis

Introduction

The pottery manufacturing process is not a series of random actions, but a sequence of conscious and planned steps undertaken by potters who aim to produce ceramic vessels with specific attributes that meet certain criteria, while using available raw materials and acquired skills (*Nicklin 1971; Roux et al. 2017; Eramo 2020; Gliozzo 2020a*). Potters may choose materials not only based on their availability but also due to other factors. For example, some clays are more suitable for wheel-thrown pottery (*Hunt 2017, 96–98*). Simultaneously, the properties of clay can be enhanced by different types of non-plastic inclusions, chosen according to their intended role in the ceramic

fabric and the customs of potters' communities (*Schiffer – Skibo 1987; Orton et al. 2004, 115; Mangel 2016, 29–32; Hunt 2017, 102–103*). Such culturally determined preferences for certain types of tempers have been observed, for example, at the site of Jagodnjak-Krčevine in Croatia, occupied from the Neolithic to the Middle Ages (*Neral et al. 2023*).

Vessel shaping follows material preparation and usually involves several steps to create a roughout and finalise the vessel's shape (*Thér et al. 2015, 47; Hunt 2017, 104–105*). Rotational devices can serve various functions during the shaping process. One such method is wheel-throwing, in which the vessel is formed entirely on the potter's wheel, allowing faster and more uniform vessel production. However, in comparison with other uses of rotational motion during shaping, this technique requires more extensive training. Together with socio-economic and cultural factors, this could have played a role in the spread and adoption of wheel-throwing (*Jeffra 2011, 106–107; Thér et al. 2015, 28–29; Běhounková 2018; Thér 2020*).

Most traces left by the shaping process are removed during vessel finishing before firing. Nevertheless, the level of attention paid by the potter to the final appearance of the vessel is an important indicator of the significance of its visual attributes, as vessels made from identical materials and by the same techniques may still differ in the emphasis placed on appearance (*Jeffra 2011, 200–202*). Vessels can be then fired in various types of firing devices, both open and closed. Each type of firing device has its own advantages (*Mangel 2016, 44–49; Roux 2019, 111–116; Gliozzo 2020b*). However, the firing process depends not only on the firing device, but also on other factors, including the firing atmosphere, which can be actively controlled by the potter to produce, for example, light or dark surfaces and pottery of different colours, even when the same raw materials are used (*Thér et al. 2015, 66–72; Roux 2019, 101, 111*).

Overall, the customs and beliefs of communities play an important role in all stages of pottery production (*Santacreu 2017; Montana 2020, 1–2*), as a sense of belonging to their community is strengthened by the transmission of knowledge and skills across generations of potters (*Nicklin 1971; Arnold 2005; Berg 2018, 97*). As a result, potters may not be interested in producing vessels that do not follow the norms of their communities (*Spataro – Meadows 2013, 72*), considering their own manufacturing process superior to the techniques of potters from other communities (*Roux et al. 2017*). The spread of the same styles and techniques across a larger territory requires stable and active networks of contacts and knowledge sharing among potters (*Jeffra 2011, 27–28; Santacreu 2017*).

Understanding such processes necessitates recognising that material culture does not represent a passive reflection of a community, but a flexible set of elements shaped by behavioural patterns and serving diverse social roles, with individual elements being preserved or replaced depending on multiple factors, including the cultural and socio-economic development, the intensity of contacts, and human mobility (*Pohl 2010; Burmeister 2013; Ulf 2014; Fernández-Götz 2019*). Consequently, the spread of a shared material culture, including pottery, can result from interactions among communities, the nature of which varies depending on the characteristics of the interacting groups (*Burmeister 2020*), and is not necessarily the consequence of large-scale population migrations and the forced assimilation of pre-existing communities (*Berg 2018*). Furthermore, human mobility takes various forms, has diverse causes, occurs over different distances, and involves distinct parts of society. Therefore, it should not be understood as a uniform process driven by a single reason (*Fernández-Götz 2019; Danielisová 2023; Schönfelder 2024*).

Because of its connection with social, economic, and other processes within society, pottery can be used as a valuable source of data on contacts between communities, the spread and interaction of distinct manufacturing traditions, as well as the development of settlement patterns (*Orton et al. 2004, 23–35*). As such, pottery is one of the key sources of information on the transformations that

occurred in Central Europe during the first century BC, at the end of the La Tène Period and the beginning of the Roman Period, corresponding to stages LT D1 and LT D2. In Bohemia and neighbouring regions, La Tène settlement reached its peak during phase LT D1a (130/100–80/70 BC), but began to decline in the subsequent phase LT D1b (80/70–50/40 BC). During stage LT D2 (50/40–10/5 BC), corresponding to stage A of the Roman Period, settlement structure, long-distance contacts, the economic system, and material culture underwent substantial changes (*Beneš et al. 2018*, 90–91; *Danielisová 2020*, 136–145). In the archaeological record, this transformation is associated with the spread of the Großromstedt culture from Central Germany, traditionally interpreted as a result of large-scale migration (*Droberjar 2006*).

Nevertheless, in Northwestern Bohemia, several assemblages dated to the stage LT D1, including those from Jenišův Újezd (Teplice District), Lužice (Chomutov District), and Radovesice (Teplice District), contain both Late La Tène pottery and pottery attributable to the Przeworsk culture and, more generally, to communities northwest of the Krušné hory. These assemblages, particularly that from Lužice, were discussed by V. Salač, who assigned them to a transitional horizon between the La Tène and Roman Periods and interpreted them as a possible result of an initial migration from Thuringia. However, the question of whether the incoming communities came into contact with the local population and whether pottery of both cultures was used contemporaneously remained unresolved. Furthermore, V. Salač noted that, although pottery attributable to the Przeworsk culture is present in the assemblage from Lužice, its non-La Tène ceramic component shows the greatest overall similarity to the Großromstedt culture (*Salač 1993*, 165–172, 175–176, 199–200; *1995*). E. Droberjar (*2006*, 20–22) interpreted these mixed assemblages, including that from Lužice, as evidence of the spread of the Przeworsk culture into Bohemia during phase LT D1b, before the subsequent larger-scale expansion of the Großromstedt culture during stage LT D2. Population mobility during stage LT D1 may have been one of the accompanying phenomena of the transformation of society and the socio-economic network at the end of the La Tène Period.

Przeworsk-like pottery from Northwestern Bohemia was dated to A2–A3 stages of the Przeworsk culture (*Beneš et al. 2017*, 42–45; *Danielisová 2020*, 141–143). Stage A2 encompasses the second half of the second century BC, the transitional phase A2/A3 represents the first half of the first century BC, and stage A3 corresponds to stage LT D2 (*Dąbrowska 1988*, 62; *Łuczkiwicz 2020*, Fig. 1). However, these mixed assemblages have been studied primarily through comparisons of vessel shapes and decoration, with only limited attention paid to materials and manufacturing techniques. They can also be compared with similar assemblages from other parts of Central Europe in order to gain new information on the possible relationships between the communities producing La Tène and Przeworsk pottery.

The aim of this article is to analyse pottery attributable to the Late La Tène and the Przeworsk cultures from the Lužice assemblage using a multi-method analytical approach combining spatial and fragmentation analysis, macroscopic observation, X-ray fluorescence (XRF), and thin-section analysis. The results allow comparison of pottery of both archaeological cultures not only in terms of shapes and surface treatment, but also fragmentation, manufacturing techniques, and materials used, including their potential provenance.

Context of the settlement at Lužice

Archaeological setting

The settlement at Lužice was located in the region of middle Ohře (Fig. 1). Sources of stone used to produce quernstones are known in the region, including, for example, quartzite named after the former village of Bešice, located 4.5 km to the northeast of Lužice. Other raw material sources are

also known in the region. A long-distance route most likely followed the Ohře River from Upper Franconia and, in this region, divided into two branches, one leading to Central Bohemia and the other to the Bílina region. The region of middle Ohře was also connected with the Plzeň region and Bavaria (*Salač 1993*, 5–6; *Salač – Kubálek 2015*, 11, Obr. 1).

La Tène settlement in the region was concentrated primarily along Ohře and its tributaries, especially the right-bank tributary Liboc (Fig. 2). Most archaeological evidence from the Late La Tène Period is represented only by solitary finds or isolated features. Nevertheless, approximately 6.2 km to the southeast of Lužice, in the area of the village of Soběsuky (Fig. 2:2), now within the cadastral area of Chbany, a settlement agglomeration occupied between the 6th and 1st centuries BC was identified. Recovered artefacts included painted pottery and 189 grinding stones made from at least 13 types of raw materials (*Waldhauser 2001*, 453–454). Another large Late La Tène settlement was located 5.4 km northeast of Lužice, in the cadastral area of Březno u Chomutova (Fig. 2:3) (*Waldhauser 2001*, 166).

The site of the former village of Lužice (Fig. 2:1) was located approximately 1 700 m north of the Nechanice reservoir, on the banks of the Lužice stream. In 1983, due to the threat posed by mining activities, a rescue excavation was carried out at Lužice covering an area of eight ha. Multiple features from different Periods were excavated, including four huts and three settlement pits dated to La Tène stages LT B–LT D, as well as one pit dated to stage B1 of the Roman Period (*Smrž 1994*, 345, 352–358).

The La Tène features included hut 9/81, measuring 700 × 350 × 40 cm and oriented along a southeast–northwest axis. In its northwest corner, a hearth measuring 100 cm in diameter was found, together with two pits approximately 50 cm deep and filled with charcoal. Above the hearth, a fragment of a quernstone was recovered, overlain by a 10 cm-thick layer of ceramic fragments. Other finds from the feature included a bronze fibula of Beltz type, Var. J., recovered from the bottom of the northwestern pit, a fragment of another bronze fibula, part of an iron fibula, a fragment of a blue glass bracelet from the upper 10 cm of the feature fill, and other small bronze, iron, and bone artefacts.

After excavation, the finds were divided according to whether they had been recovered from depths of up to 10 cm, from depths greater than 10 cm, from postholes, or from the northwestern pit. *Z. Smrž (1991)* dated the assemblage to stages LT D1–LT D2. Other La Tène features at the settlement were older, with the exception of feature 13, representing a superposition of huts dated to LT B and LT D stages. However, hut 9/81 was situated several tens of metres from this group, and in its vicinity only one pit with finds from stage LT B was identified (*Salač 1993*, 71, 165–175; *1995*, 146–150). Finds from the Lužice settlement are currently deposited in the Regional Museum in Chomutov.

Geological setting

The geological setting of the site is characterised by anthropogenic deposits of variable composition overlying sediments of the western part of the Tertiary Most Basin. These are represented predominantly by clay and sandy clay of the Most Formation. Upper Cretaceous sediments of the Bílá Hora Formation constitute the westernmost occurrence of the Bohemian Cretaceous Basin in this region. Their outcrops are restricted to small areas in the vicinity of the site. The formation is composed mainly of quartz sandstones, particularly along the Krušné hory Fault zone, reaches a thickness of approximately 30–130 m, and is dated to the Lower Turonian (*Misař et al. 1983*, *Czech Geological Survey 2026*).

Immediately west of the site lies the distinctive geological complex of the Doupov Mountains, a large Tertiary stratovolcanic structure that forms a prominent feature of the regional landscape. It

is composed of volcanoclastic deposits, including tuffs and tuffites, lava flows represented mainly by basanites and olivine basalts, and numerous magmatic dykes and intrusive bodies.

The oldest geological unit in the broader region is the Saxothuringian Zone, which occupies extensive areas north-west of Lužice. It consists of a diverse assemblage of metamorphic rocks, including orthogneisses, paragneisses, granulites, granulitic gneisses, amphibolites, serpentinites, eclogites, limestones, and dolomites. The Ohře River, flowing eastwards from the Saxothuringian Zone towards the study area, has transported material derived from both metamorphic and volcanic source rocks and thus represents an important potential source of raw materials within the local sedimentary environment.

Quaternary deposits in the vicinity of Lužice are represented mainly by fluvial sediments associated with the Ohře River and its tributaries. These deposits typically consist of sands, gravels, and loams. Deluvial sediments of sandy-loamy composition are also common. In addition, relatively extensive loess deposits occur several kilometres south and east of the site, providing another important sedimentary component of the regional landscape.

Material and methods

Material and cultural attribution

The ceramic assemblage analysed in this article originated from feature 9/81 in Lužice and consisted of 2 361 pottery fragments. In total, 105 ceramic fragments could be attributed to the La Tène culture and 47 to the Przeworsk culture. The cultural attribution of the pottery was based primarily on studies of the assemblage from Lužice by V. Salač (1993, 167–172; 1995, Abb. 6–11).

The pottery attributable to the La Tène culture included forms with analogies at other Late La Tène sites in Northwestern Bohemia (*Drda 1977; Koutecký – Venclová 1979; Salač 1990; Koutecký 1997*), as well as at settlements in other parts of Bohemia (*Čížmář 1989; Danielisová 2010, 69–73; Pleska 2015, 59–61, 67, 90–93*). Parallels to Przeworsk-like pottery could be then found at various Late La Tène and pre-Roman Iron Age settlements, including Gorsleben (*Seidel 2017*) and Kleinschwabhausen in Thuringia (*Grasselt 2017*), Muschenheim in Hesse (*Meyer 1994*), Sosnowiec (*Teska – Michałowski 2017*), Daniszew, Kielpiny, Jaromierz, and Kalisz-Dobrzec in Greater Poland (*Żychliński – Teska 2017*), Magnuszew Duży and Tomaszewo in the eastern part of Central Poland (*Prochowicz 2017*), and Brodno in Lower Silesia (*Błażejowski 2017*). In addition, a number of vessel shapes also have general parallels in assemblages from the Early Roman Period, not only at Jenišův Újezd in Northwestern Bohemia (*Koutecký 1997*), but also, for example, at the settlement of Slepovice in Eastern Bohemia (*Jilek et al. 2013, 54–62*).

For the purposes of statistical analysis, cultural attribution was divided into three classification categories: LT D1 (Late La Tène pottery), A2 (Przeworsk-like pottery and pottery of generally Early Roman character), and NA (pottery not attributable to either of the two groups). Cultural attribution was based on vessel morphology, rim shapes, decoration, and surface treatment. Material properties and traces left by the shaping process were not used for cultural attribution.

Spatial and fragmentation analysis

Pottery attributable to the La Tène and Przeworsk cultures was evaluated based on its distribution within the feature, specifically according to whether fragments were recovered in the first 10 cm of the feature fill, at greater depths, in postholes, or in pits at the bottom of the feature (Tab. 1). This analysis was complemented by an assessment of pottery fragmentation. Fragmentation reflects formation processes, including post-depositional transformations, that affect all artefacts

(*Neustupný 2007*, 51–53; *Brönnimann et al. 2020*). These processes influence formal, spatial, quantitative, and other attributes of archaeological finds (*Schiffer 1987*, 15–21).

Formation processes play an important role in the development of archaeological features and their individual layers. These layers may result from human activity, for example through ground levelling or the secondary use of features for waste disposal, or from natural processes (*Kuna et al. 2012*, 23–25, 33–34). Variability in the character and rate of layer formation was studied, for example, at the La Tène settlement of Basel-Gasfabrik in Switzerland (*Brönnimann et al. 2020*). Depending on the relationship between an object and its place of deposition, it is possible to distinguish primary waste, in which an object is deposited at its place of use, secondary waste, which results from the intentional relocation of discarded objects to another place (*Schiffer 1987*, 58–64), and tertiary waste, in which objects originally deposited on the surface are transferred into features by natural processes. Consequently, the fill of a feature is not necessarily of the same age as the feature itself (*Neustupný 2007*, 66, 69–72).

However, transformative processes, such as fragmentation, reduction, and accumulation (*Neustupný 1996*, 502–506; *2007*, 54–62), represent not only a challenge for the evaluation of assemblages, but also an opportunity to study the formation of layers within archaeological features, as individual layers may have formed at dissimilar rates and through distinct processes (*Kuna et al. 2012*, 23–25, 33–34). Quantitative analysis of pottery assemblages can be used, for example, to study the spatial and quantitative relationships between pottery attributable to different cultures or Periods within the fill of an archaeological feature.

As a first step, the weight and average wall thickness of each ceramic fragment from feature 9/81 were measured. These values were then used to calculate the Index of Fragmentation ($\text{fragment weight}/0.1724 \times \text{fragment wall thickness}^{1.7974}$), a method proposed by M. Kuna and N. Profantová (*2005*, 123–124) based on pottery recovered from surface surveys. Therefore, a value of one indicates that a fragment corresponds to the average level of fragmentation observed among the surface finds, none of which exceeded a value of five. In general, fragments with lower values are typically small sherds interpreted as refuse originally lying on the ground and only secondarily deposited into sunken features. In contrast, fragments with values above 10 may represent parts of broken vessels thrown directly into a sunken feature at the end of their use.

Macroscopic observation

The entire available pottery assemblage from Lužice was classified using macroscopic observation (Fig. 3) to document pottery characteristics and variability (Online Supplementary Material 1). Based on the resulting data, 30 samples were selected for chemical analysis to adequately represent different material categories, technologies, styles, and archaeological cultures (Fig. 4–5; Online Supplementary Material 2–3).

Each fragment was classified using the following variables: material category (Mat), proportion of inclusions (InMn), variability of inclusions (InVar), types of inclusions (In), traces left by the shaping process, the coloration of a cross-section (Vy), surface treatment (Po), vessel morphology, and rim attributes (Online Supplementary Material 4–5).

The variable Mat described the size and sorting of inclusions within ceramic fabrics, ranging from the finest to the coarsest (Mat1–Mat5). Further classification of inclusions involved the evaluation of their proportion in the ceramic matrix using the ordinal variable InMn (InMn1–InMn3) (based on *Orton et al. 2004*, 238–240). Inclusions also varied in colour and shape. Therefore, the ordinal variable InVar was defined to distinguish three categories of pottery (InVar1–InVar3). In addition, the types and combinations of inclusions were described in more detail by the nominal variable In,

whose categories (In1–In13) were defined based on previous studies of La Tène pottery (Venclová *et al.* 1998, 82; Danielisová 2010, 67–69).

Following the material evaluation, traces left by the shaping process visible on the pottery surface were evaluated to determine whether they could be associated with hand-made pottery, wheel-made pottery, or pottery shaped by a combination of both methods (Jeffra 2011, 56–57, 115–136; Běhounková 2018; Thér 2020). To assess variation in the firing process, the alternation of light and dark layers visible on the cross-sections of fragments (the variable Vy) was recorded using the Munsell Book of Soil Colour Charts to improve colour differentiation (Orton *et al.* 2004, 133–135, Fig. 11.1; Thér *et al.* 2015, 66–72).

In the subsequent stage of macroscopic observation, surface treatment (Po) was classified into nine categories (Po1–Po9) of smooth (Po1–Po3) and rough (Po4–Po9) surfaces, based on the typology created by N. Venclová (1998, 90–91; 2008, Obr. 50) for pottery from the La Tène Period in Bohemia. Vessels were further classified into four morphological groups according to the ratio of their maximum diameter to their height and the shape of their contours (Rice 1987, 215–219). Finally, three rim attributes were evaluated: direction (Op), thickening (Oz), and lip trimming (Os), using the typology of K. Sklenář (1998, 7) and studies of La Tène pottery (Pleska 2015, 64–65; Repka 2020, 51–52).

Ceramic petrography

After sampling, all 30 specimens were ground in an agate grinding jar using a Retsch PM 100 planetary ball mill. The chemical composition was determined using a Rigaku Nex CG energy-dispersive X-ray fluorescence spectrometer (ED-XRF), equipped with a 50 W Pd anode and a silicon drift detector (SDD) with a resolution of up to 145 eV. The samples were analysed as pressed powder pellets. The resulting chemical dataset (Online Supplementary Material 6), comprising the concentrations of Al, Si, K, Ca, Ti, V, Mn, Fe, Ni, Cu, As, Rb, Sr, Ba, and Pb, was statistically evaluated by principal component analysis (PCA) using the FactoMineR package in R (Lê *et al.* 2008). The scores of the first four principal components were further used for hierarchical clustering (Online Supplementary Material 7) (Husson *et al.* 2010).

Standard petrographic thin sections, 30 µm thick, were prepared from 13 samples selected based on the results of X-ray fluorescence and analysed using a Zeiss Axioscope 5 polarising microscope (Online Supplementary Material 8). The descriptive methodology applied in this study follows, with minor modifications, the approaches of Gregerová *et al.* (2010) and Quinn (2013). Inclusion frequency was expressed using a semi-quantitative scoring system similar to that proposed by Sauer and Waksman (2005), and described in greater detail in the author's doctoral dissertation (Slaviček 2023).

Statistical data analysis

Data collected during macroscopic observation were analysed in RStudio (R version 4.2.2). The initial evaluation used the packages dplyr for data organisation (Wickham *et al.* 2023), skimr for summarising data distributions (Waring *et al.* 2022), and ggplot2 for data visualisation (Wickham 2016). Relationships between cultural attribution (A2, LT D1, and NA), the Index of Fragmentation, and context within the feature were visualised and examined using boxplots.

In the next stage of the statistical analysis, contingency tables were created to study relationships between cultural attribution and other categorical variables (Online Supplementary Material 9–10). These tables were used to conduct a Chi-square test of independence (χ^2) and calculate Cramer's *V* (Tab. 2–3). However, some categories of the analysed variables were excluded from these analyses. Specifically, surface treatments Po6 and Po9, thickening of the rim Oz4, and lip trimming Os1

were excluded because they were used for cultural attribution. Categories with a total frequency of three or fewer observations were also excluded from further statistical analyses.

The Chi-square test was used to test for statistically significant associations between cultural attribution and other categorical variables, including chemical groups (*Baxter 2015*, 202–206; *Carlson 2017*, 190–193). Cramer's V , calculated using the *rstatix* package (*Kassambara 2023*), was then applied to assess the strength of association, where values range from zero (no association) to one (perfect association) (*Hendel 2015*, 323; *Carlson 2017*, 196).

Results

Spatial and fragmentation analysis

Both La Tène and Przeworsk pottery was present in all parts of the feature, with 58.1% of the pottery attributable to the La Tène culture recovered from depths greater than 10 cm. Przeworsk pottery, on the other hand, was distributed relatively evenly across all parts of the feature except for postholes. In the pit at the bottom of the feature, pottery attributable to both archaeological cultures was present in almost equal numbers. The Chi-square test did not indicate a statistically significant association between cultural attribution and parts of the feature ($\chi^2 = 7.544$, $df = 3$, $p = 0.056$; Cramer's $V = 0.223$).

Higher values of Index of Fragmentation, indicating better-preserved vessel fragments, were generally recorded in the assemblage of Przeworsk pottery, particularly at depths greater than 10 cm. Przeworsk pottery from this part of the feature consistently exhibited values that, elsewhere in the feature and within the La Tène assemblage, occurred only as outliers. This part of the feature also showed the greatest variability in fragmentation values within the Przeworsk assemblage.

By contrast, fragmentation of Przeworsk pottery in the upper 10 cm of the feature was not significantly different from that of La Tène pottery. Likewise, pottery of both cultures in the pit at the bottom of the feature showed similar distributions of fragmentation values. This variation in the fragmentation of Przeworsk pottery across individual parts of the feature was not identified in the assemblage of La Tène pottery, whose fragmentation, particularly in the median values, was relatively analogous across all parts of the feature.

The clearest distinctions in fragmentation between Przeworsk and La Tène pottery occurred at depths greater than 10 cm, whereas the greatest similarity was found in the pit at the bottom of the feature. Culturally unattributable pottery showed comparable Index of Fragmentation values in all parts of the feature, with the exception of postholes. Overall, culturally unattributable pottery generally had lower median values of Index of Fragmentation than culturally attributable pottery (Fig. 6).

Classification based on macroscopic observation

Chi-square test (Tab. 2) did not detect an association between cultural attribution and the variables Mat, InMn, InVar, or In. Przeworsk pottery appeared to contain fewer categories of inclusions (In), but pottery of both archaeological cultures showed similar patterns in the most frequent inclusion categories. For La Tène pottery, the most common categories were In8 (40.2 %), In3 (19.6 %), and In11 (18.6 %), while for Przeworsk pottery, these were In8 (36.2 %), In3 (27.7 %), and In9 (12.8 %).

Chi-square test showed an association between cultural attribution and traces left by the shaping process (Tab. 2; Cramer's $V = 0.282$). Traces associated with wheel-made vessels were characteristic of La Tène pottery. Furthermore, only La Tène pottery had roughened surfaces of categories Po6 and Po9, while the surface of Przeworsk pottery was usually smooth (categories Po1, Po2, and Po3). Homogeneous dark cross-sectional colouring (category Vy1) was then the most common cross-sectional colouring of both La Tène (38.3 %) and Przeworsk pottery (34 %), but the proportions of other categories varied slightly, especially in the case of multilayered categories (Vy5, Vy6 and Vy7), with category Vy5 being more characteristic of La Tène pottery (26.2 % compared with 15.9 %) and category Vy6 being more characteristic of Przeworsk pottery (22.7 % compared with 7.7 %).

Cramer's V indicated the strongest association between cultural attribution and morphological groups (Cramer's $V = 0.399$), followed by the rim attributes Os (Cramer's $V = 0.378$), Oz (Cramer's $V = 0.447$), and Op (Cramer's $V = 0.532$). Only the group of Przeworsk pottery contained short shapes with broken contours (group vpn). Przeworsk pottery was also characterised by vertical (Op5) and sharply obliquely everted rims (Op7), while La Tène pottery most often had curved (Op10) and inward-curved (Op11) rims. Additionally, mallet-shaped thickening of the rims (Oz1) occurred only on Przeworsk pottery, whose rims were otherwise mostly (63.6 %) non-thickened (Oz2). The La Tène pottery group was more variable in this regard, with only 41.2 % of its rims being non-thickened. Faceted lips (Os1) were exclusive to Przeworsk pottery, while pointed lips (Os7) were limited to La Tène pottery, whose rims were most often (68.6 %) untrimmed (Os2), whereas rims of Przeworsk pottery were untrimmed in only 27.3 % of cases.

Ceramic petrography

The pottery assemblage was divided into five groups (Tab. 4) on the basis of hierarchical clustering of principal components derived from elemental concentrations (Online Supplementary Material 7). Chi-square test did not indicate an association between XRF chemical groups and the cultural attribution of pottery (Tab. 3). Nevertheless, while La Tène pottery was present in all five groups, Przeworsk pottery was concentrated in groups XRF4 and XRF5 and was predominant only in subgroup XRF5b (Tab. 5). No chemical group was exclusive to Przeworsk pottery.

Selected samples representing the XRF groups were subsequently analysed by thin-section petrography, allowing the identification and description of individual ceramic fabrics (Online Supplementary Material 6; Online Supplementary Material 8). The results show that the largest chemical cluster corresponds to a petrographically slightly heterogeneous group, defined here as Fabric A. The secondary cluster comprises a set of diverse samples, each characterised by a specific petrographic feature. Although these samples cannot be subsumed under a single fabric, their petrographic composition is not sufficiently exotic to warrant classification as outliers. Only one sample fulfils the criteria of an outlier, both in terms of its chemical and petrographic composition.

Fabric A represents the main petrographic group and includes seven samples: L-602, L-665, L-1103, L-1105, L-1107, L-1430 and L-1432. The ceramic raw material can be characterised as silty clay. The microstructure is non-parallel to weakly parallel, while the texture is mostly very poorly sorted. Non-plastic inclusions account for approximately 30 vol% on average. Some samples display slight signs of bimodality, although this feature is generally weakly developed. The larger, sand-sized grains are predominantly subrounded and equant in shape (Fig. 7: A, B).

The most diagnostic petrographic feature of this fabric is the abundant occurrence of metaquartzite fragments, together with granitoid rock fragments, which range from occasional to frequent. Volcanic rock fragments are less common and occur mostly rarely. Mica schist and chert were identified in a few samples, again mostly as rare components. A noteworthy feature is a large lump

of calcareous clay in sample L-1103. Individual mineral grains are represented mainly by quartz, which is frequent to abundant. Alkali feldspar and plagioclase occur from occasional to common. Muscovite is common, whereas biotite is rare to occasional. Accessory minerals include pyroxene, with variable abundance ranging from rare to frequent, and amphibole, which shows a similar range from trace to common. Tourmaline occurs only in trace amounts, while garnet was observed in two samples, where it is occasional to common. Micritic calcite, apart from its occurrence in sample L-1103, was also recorded rarely in sample L-665. The rare occurrence of sillimanite in sample L-602 is also worth noting.

Fabric A indicates firing under mixed oxidising and reducing conditions. Most samples display an oxidised zone along the external surface, extending to variable depths within the ceramic body. In some cases, oxidation is so extensive that the samples are almost completely oxidised. The firing temperature was probably relatively low, as indicated by the predominantly moderate intensity of biotite pleochroism. As with the firing atmosphere, the firing temperature was not homogeneous. It likely varied both between individual firing events and according to the position of the vessel within the firing structure, broadly within the range of approximately 700–900 °C.

Sample L-772 represents **Fabric B**. Its diagnostic characteristics are a finer grain size than that observed in Fabric A and a relatively high proportion of finely platy biotite dispersed within the clay matrix (Fig. 7: C). Non-plastic inclusions account for approximately 15 vol.% in total. The fabric displays a bimodal grain-size distribution and contains, in addition to a silty component of approximately 5 vol.%, fine to very fine sand temper, representing about 10 vol.%. Compared with Fabric A, Fabric B differs not only in the higher abundance of biotite in the matrix, but also in the lower proportion of metaquartzite fragments, which are only common, granitoid fragments, which are rare, as well as feldspars and accessory minerals. Occasional plant tissue remains were also observed. The fabric was fired predominantly under oxidising conditions, although a thin reduced zone occurs along the surface. Biotite is only weakly pleochroic, suggesting firing temperatures in the range of approximately 800–900 °C.

Fabric C consists solely of sample L-1760, whose petrographic composition differs significantly from that of the preceding fabrics (Fig. 7: D). Metaquartzite fragments were not observed, whereas granitoid rock fragments are abundant. Muscovite occurs only in trace amounts, while biotite is abundant. In addition, quartz is abundant, alkali feldspar is frequent, and plagioclase was not identified. Amphibole occurs only rarely. The non-plastic inclusions show a strongly bimodal grain-size distribution. The silty component accounts for only approximately 5 vol.%, whereas the temper fraction reaches up to 30 vol.%. Both the internal and external surfaces of the sample are oxidised. The oxidised zone extending from the external surface penetrates almost to the centre of the ceramic body, where it gives way to a reduced core. By contrast, the oxidised zone along the internal surface is only thin. Biotite locally displays moderate pleochroism, suggesting firing temperatures in the range of approximately 750–850 °C.

Fabric D is represented by sample L-1113. Its defining features are a clay-rich matrix containing less than 1 vol.% of silty material and a strongly bimodal grain-size distribution (Fig. 7: E). The temper (sandy fraction) accounts for approximately 30 vol.% and consists of equant, angular to subrounded sand-sized grains, dominated by abundant granitoid rock fragments. Apart from the absence of metaquartzite fragments and pyroxene, neither of which was identified in this sample, the petrographic composition is broadly similar to that of Fabric A. The firing features are also comparable to those observed in the other fabrics, indicating mixed firing conditions with an oxidised surface layer. Biotite displays strong pleochroism, suggesting a relatively low firing temperature of approximately 700 °C.

Fabric E is represented by sample L-847 and is the only fabric tempered with grog (Fig. 7: F). Its overall mineralogical composition is comparable to that of Fabric A, particularly in terms of the abundance and relative proportions of feldspars and micas. The rock fragments are also broadly similar to those observed in Fabric A: metamorphic quartzite is common, granitoid fragments are occasional, and rare fragments of metamorphic rocks, including mica schist and gneiss, are also present. The sample displays oxidised margins, whereas most of the core is reduced and optically inactive. This suggests a higher firing temperature, probably in the range of approximately 900–1050 °C.

Fabric F is represented by sample L-638 and is the only specimen of graphite-tempered pottery in the assemblage. Graphite occurs both as discrete grains, where it is frequent, and as a component of graphite-bearing metaquartzite fragments, which are common, and gneiss fragments, which occur occasionally (Fig. 7: G). The overall mineralogical composition is again broadly comparable to that of Fabric A. Noteworthy components include occasional fibrous sillimanite and occasional amphibolite fragments. The sample also indicates a mixed firing atmosphere. The firing temperature was probably within the same range as that inferred for most of the assemblage, approximately 800–900 °C, based on the weak pleochroism of biotite.

The only defined **outlier** within the assemblage is sample L-1349. It is distinguished by the predominance of limonitised rock fragments composed mainly of alkali feldspar and quartz (Fig. 7: H). Opaque to dark red material fills the intergranular spaces and numerous fractures within the feldspar grains. These clasts account for approximately 30 vol.% of the sample and most likely represent intentionally added temper. Other rock types are only rare to occasional - sillimanite gneiss, mica schist, magmatic rock with pyroxene amphibole and quartz. Biotite is frequent, in contrast to only occasional muscovite, and exhibits weak pleochroism, indicating a firing temperature in the range of approximately 800–900 °C. The peculiar petrographic composition of this sample is further complemented by traces of isolated graphite grains.

Discussion

Provenance

The petrographic composition of Fabrics A to E suggests that these fabrics are broadly related in terms of raw material provenance. Although they differ in the relative proportions of micas, granitoid fragments, metamorphic quartzite fragments and other metamorphic lithoclasts, they share a comparable overall mineralogical and lithological spectrum. Volcanic rock fragments occur only as minor components. This composition points to a raw material source influenced primarily by crystalline rocks of the Saxothuringian Zone, with only a limited contribution from volcanic material.

A plausible mechanism by which such material could have reached the vicinity of the site is fluvial transport by the Ohře River. The river flows close by the site and partly skirts the volcanic complex of the Doupov Mountains, while also draining areas with crystalline rocks of Saxothuringian affinity further upstream. The ceramic fabrics may therefore reflect the use of alluvial or redeposited sediments containing a mixture of crystalline-derived clasts and minor volcanic components. At the current stage of research, however, it is not possible to determine whether comparable proportions of these lithologies occur in the Ohře alluvial deposits directly around the site, or whether the raw material source should be sought further upstream.

The interpretation of the rock fragments must also take into account the limitations of ceramic micropetrography. The lithoclasts were classified mainly as metaquartzite and granitoid fragments, but their small size makes precise petrographic determination difficult. If the proposed connection

with the Saxothuringian Zone is correct, at least some fragments identified as granitoids may in fact represent metamorphosed granitoids, particularly orthogneisses. Similarly, some metaquartzite grains may derive from gneissic rocks as well. Nevertheless, the presence of genuine granitoid fragments cannot be excluded.

If some of the granitoid fragments are indeed primary granitoids rather than metamorphosed equivalents, more distant source areas must also be considered. The Čistá–Jesenice Massif, located more than 25 km south of the site, may represent a possible source, especially for Fabric C, because of its abundance in biotite. Another potential source is the Krušné hory/Erzgebirge batholith, situated approximately 30 km or more to the west. For most fabrics, however, the predominance of muscovite, together with the occurrence of mica schist, gneiss and sillimanite, more strongly supports a connection with metamorphic rocks of the Saxothuringian Zone.

The minor but repeated occurrence of pyroxene and sporadic volcanic rock fragments adds a further component to this provenance model. These inclusions suggest that the raw material may have been collected from sediments formed in a contact zone where material derived from the Doupov volcanic complex mixed with clasts derived from Saxothuringian crystalline rocks. Such a geological setting is available close to the site and provides a reasonable explanation for the mixed petrographic signature observed in the main fabrics.

Fabric F, the graphite-tempered fabric, should be treated separately. Its graphite-bearing inclusions indicate a more specific source component that is not characteristic of the other fabrics. Potential source areas include graphite-bearing rocks known from the region north-east of Jáchymov, approximately 25 km west of Lužice.

The provenance of the sample classified as an outlier is also most probably related to the Saxothuringian Zone, as suggested by the presence of graphite, albeit only in trace amounts, together with lithoclasts of several metamorphic rock types. At this stage, however, a more precise determination of the source of the limonitised clasts and feldspar-rich material is not possible. The primary source rock was very likely granitoid in composition.

Comparing pottery attributable to the La Tène and Przeworsk cultures

While both La Tène and Przeworsk pottery were present in all parts of the feature, certain dissimilarities in distribution and fragmentation could be observed. La Tène pottery was mainly concentrated at depths greater than 10 cm, but its sherds from different parts of the feature showed little variation in Index of Fragmentation values. Przeworsk pottery, on the other hand, was distributed relatively evenly throughout the feature, but its fragmentation varied depending on the part of the feature. This appears to imply that pottery of both cultures underwent distinct formation processes before being deposited into the feature and differ both in origin and date (*Neustupný 1996, 502–506; 2007, 51–55; Kuna – Profantová 2005, 120–122*).

Furthermore, the fill of the feature was most likely formed through multiple depositional phases, at least according to the distribution of culturally attributable pottery. In the case of the bottom pit, the comparable quantity and fragmentation of La Tène and Przeworsk pottery indicated their possible contemporaneous deposition, with fragmentation corresponding to tertiary waste. A contrasting situation was identified in the fill below the upper 10 cm and above the bottom pit. La Tène pottery from this context was highly fragmented and relatively homogeneous in its Index of Fragmentation values and could be interpreted as waste originally lying on the surface and subsequently deposited into the feature by natural processes, or potentially as part of a human-made ground levelling. The high values and variability of the Index of Fragmentation of Przeworsk pottery, on the other hand, support the interpretation of secondary waste directly deposited into an abandoned feature later reused as a refuse pit. However, the upper fill of the feature was more

similar to the assemblage from the bottom pit (*Kuna – Profantová 2005*, 123–124; *Kuna et al. 2012*, 23–25, 33–34; *Brönnimann et al. 2020*).

Overall, the fact that the majority of both culturally attributable and unattributable pottery showed fragmentation values associated with tertiary waste complicates the evaluation of their chronological relationships, especially because contemporaneous deposition does not necessarily imply contemporaneous use or even production. In addition, culturally unattributable pottery showed predominantly low Index of Fragmentation values in all parts of the feature. These values did not vary substantially across different contexts, indicating that most of the culturally unattributable pottery was deposited into the feature as tertiary waste, in the form of small ceramic sherds originally lying on the ground surface (*Neustupný 2007*, 66–74; *Brönnimann et al. 2020*). Nevertheless, the analysis suggests that the fill of the feature was likely not the result of a single event and that pottery of both cultures was deposited together throughout the formation of the fill. Consequently, neither component could be considered chronologically earlier than the other with certainty.

Analyses of materials used, production processes, and visual styles also revealed both similarities and differences between La Tène and Przeworsk pottery. Regarding the origin and processing of raw materials, no clear division was recognised. Nevertheless, La Tène pottery was more diverse in terms of the ceramic materials used. Some materials were used for pottery of both cultures, whereas no material was exclusive to Przeworsk pottery. This implies at least a partial overlap in traditions of raw material procurement and processing among the producers of both La Tène and Przeworsk pottery (*Schiffer – Skibo 1987*; *Spataro – Meadows 2013*).

Traces associated with wheel-made pottery were characteristic of La Tène pottery but occurred on some Przeworsk pottery as well. Even in the case of La Tène pottery, these traces were not more frequent than traces associated with hand-made vessels (25.7 % compared with 29.5 %). Nevertheless, macroscopically observed traces provide only indicative evidence of shaping processes, and directly linking them to a specific technology may be problematic without further analyses or experimental verification (*Thér 2020*; *Volf et al. 2024*, 31). Dissimilarities were also identified in the frequency of multilayered cross-sectional colouring, which could reflect variation in firing procedures (*Orton et al. 2004*, 133–135; *Roux 2019*, 101, 111, 209).

These differences in the production process did not necessarily indicate a lack of contacts among potters making La Tène and Przeworsk pottery but rather adherence to learned manufacturing practices and the preservation of their respective pottery production traditions. However, no type of traces left by the shaping process or cross-sectional colouring was exclusive to either La Tène or Przeworsk pottery, nor was any particular shaping or firing procedure universally applied in the production of either group. This suggests that stylistic affiliation did not necessarily correspond to a single manufacturing tradition and that potters producing either La Tène or Przeworsk pottery could employ different manufacturing practices even when making pottery of the same style (*Nicklin 1971*; *Berg 2018*).

The strongest and clearest distinctions were observable in the visual attributes of pottery, with some surface treatments, morphological vessel groups, and rim shapes being characteristic of, or even exclusive to, either La Tène or Przeworsk pottery. This implies that even when using similar materials, producers of La Tène and Przeworsk pottery preserved separate visual styles of ceramic vessels. This might be related to the specific role of the visual styles of ceramic vessels, which could serve to express affiliation with a particular social group and therefore were not normally combined. Instead, one visual style may have replaced another (*Curta 2014*; *Berg 2018*). Visual attributes, manufacturing practices, and materials used could also fulfil diverse cultural and socio-economic roles depending on their context and be shared at different levels of society, from

individual households to entire communities and supra-regional social groups (*Curta 2014; Ulf 2014; Roux et al. 2017*).

Finds displaying Przeworsk-style characteristics, such as pottery with faceted rims, also occurred in Hesse during stage LT D1. This pottery corresponded to stage A2 of the Przeworsk culture and preceded the later spread of the Großromstedt culture (*Meyer 1994, 184*). A similar development has been documented at Straubing in Bavaria, where finds reflected contacts with Central Germany and other regions, including pottery with rims typical of the Przeworsk culture (*Tappert 2007, 194–196*). In Thuringia, the relationship between La Tène and Przeworsk pottery was examined in greater detail in the southern foothills of the Harz Mountains, where pottery of both cultures was present from the Middle La Tène to the Late La Tène period. X-ray fluorescence and micropetrographic analyses showed that the pottery of both cultures was made from local materials but differed in manufacturing practices (*Daszkiewicz – Meyer 2003; Meyer 2013*).

Overall, the spread of the Przeworsk culture in Thuringia during the second and first centuries BC had various forms. New settlements emerged both at the edge of the older La Tène settlement zone, often around iron ore deposits, and within areas already occupied by La Tène settlements. Solitary finds attributable to the Przeworsk culture are also known from other La Tène settlements in the region (*Rauchfuß 2017; Seidel 2017*). At the settlement of Kleinschwabhausen, for example, both pottery characteristic of the La Tène culture and vessels displaying elements typical of the Przeworsk culture, particularly rim shapes, but not decoration, were found. Przeworsk pottery was most likely made from local materials (*Grasselt 2017*). This suggests that the spread of the Przeworsk cultural elements was not a sudden event but rather the result of diverse socio-economic processes taking place over an extended time period.

Assemblages attributable to the Przeworsk and La Tène cultures were replaced in Thuringia, Bohemia, and other regions in the second half of the first century BC by assemblages attributable to the Großromstedt culture (*Tappert 2007, 199–200; Meyer 2013; Beneš et al. 2018, 90–91*). Mixed assemblages of La Tène and Early Roman pottery share certain similarities with mixed assemblages of La Tène and Przeworsk pottery. In Slepovice in Eastern Bohemia, some types of inclusions were specific to either La Tène or Roman pottery, and there was no overlap in the fabric groups. However, no chemical group was exclusive to Early Roman pottery, just as no chemical group was exclusive to Przeworsk pottery in Lužice. Traces associated with wheel-made vessels were then exclusive to La Tène pottery, and variation was also observed in the firing process. Nevertheless, the greatest contrast existed in visual attributes, similarly to the assemblage from Lužice (*Volf et al. 2025*). More pronounced distinctions between La Tène and Early Roman pottery were identified at Mlékojedy in Central Bohemia, although overlaps in the materials used and manufacturing practices were also present (*Beneš et al. 2024*).

A comparable situation to that at Slepovice was documented at the settlement of Mardorf in Thuringia. At this settlement, changes in materials and technologies used between the La Tène and Early Roman Periods seemed to represent a gradual transition rather than a sudden change (*Daszkiewicz – Meyer 2008*). This may imply that the spread of both the Przeworsk and later the Großromstedt cultures could have been part of a long socio-economic development rather than an abrupt event. This development during the first century BC might be connected with the reorganisation of society and contact networks, accompanied by increased mobility of individuals or small groups contributing to the spread of new ceramic styles (*Burmeister 2013; Berg 2018; Fernández-Götz 2019*).

Conclusions

The use of similar raw materials may indicate access to the same or nearby raw material sources by potters producing La Tène and Przeworsk pottery and potentially also shared practices of ceramic fabric preparation. Furthermore, there was a partial overlap in the subsequent stages of pottery production. This supports the interpretation that potters were in contact and exchanged knowledge about pottery-making practices. In this model, the preservation of their respective visual styles might have served to express affiliation with larger regional or supra-regional social groups, whereas the manufacturing process itself was more variable and could have been linked to individual households or other smaller social units. Such contacts may have been facilitated by increased human mobility as part of broader processes associated with the reorganisation of society and socio-economic networks during the first century BC in Central Europe.

However, the results cannot confirm the simultaneous production of both La Tène and Przeworsk pottery with complete certainty. Moreover, the fill of the feature may have accumulated over a long-lasting Period from material of different ages that was deposited as tertiary waste. To better understand such mixed assemblages, more extensive research is required, ideally combining the approaches used in this study with additional methods, such as computed tomography for a more detailed analysis of vessel shaping procedures. Further insights may be also gained from studies of the development of settlement network, as well as of pottery and other artefacts from the preceding stages of the La Tène Period and the subsequent stages of the Roman Period.

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Data availability

Data are available in the Supplementary files and at Zenodo (Link: <https://zenodo.org/records/20394411>).

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